

EVALUATION OF THE BACTERIOLOGICAL QUALITY AND THE ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE PROFILE OF BACTERIAL FLORA ASSOCIATED WITH PROCESSED *RHYNOPHORUS PHOENICIS* LARVA SOLD IN BENIN CITY AND AMUKPE-SAPELE ROUNDABOUT.

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ABSTRACT

The bacteriological quality and the antibiotic resistance profile of the identified bacterial flora associated with processed *Rhyncophorus phoenicis* grubs was evaluated using standard microbiological procedures. The mean bacterial counts recorded for those sampled within Benin City ranged from 1.1×10^3 cfu/g \pm 0.12 to 5.9×10^3 cfu/g \pm 3.2, while the mean bacterial counts recorded for the samples collected within Amupke-Sapele ranged from 1.1×10^3 cfu/g \pm 3.1 to 3.0×10^3 cfu/g \pm 0.65. Seven bacterial isolates were characterized from the grubs and included; *Staphylococcus* sp., *Micrococcus* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Enterococcus* sp., *Corynebacterium* sp., *Listeria* sp. and *Streptococcus* sp. The most frequently isolated bacterial species isolated from roasted grubs collected in Benin City were *Bacillus* sp. and *Listeria* sp, whilst *Staphylococcus* sp. was the most dominant bacterial isolate occurring in majority of roasted grubs collected from Amukpe-Sapele roundabout. All the grub borne bacterial isolates were resistant to ceftazidime and cefuroxime. There were marked differences between the antibiotic resistance patterns exhibited by the respective bacterial isolates identified from grubs sampled in Benin City and Amukpe-Sapele. The possible ingestion of roasted grubs populated with antibiotic resistant and potentially pathogenic bacteria by unsuspecting consumers especially those with compromised immunity status is an immediate public health risk.

Key words: Bacterial flora, *Rhyncophorus phoenicis*, Roasted grub, Antibiotic resistance

INTRODUCTION

Hundreds of insect species have been utilized as human food, some of the more important groups include grasshopper, caterpillars, beetle grubs and sometimes adults, winged termites, bee, wasp and ant brood (larvae and pupae) as well as winged ants, cicadas, and a

variety of aquatic insects (Banjo *et al.*, 2006). Grubs of the raphia palm weevil, *Rhyncophorus phoenicis* (Fabr.) are fried and eaten in several areas of western Nigeria which include; Edo, Delta and Anambra states (Okore *et al.*, 2014). Active marketing of the fried grubs is known to occur in these states as these prepared grubs are hawked along major roads and markets in Edo and Delta States of Nigeria (Ekrakene and Igeleke, 2007).

The adult palm weevils are known to possess a plump, yellowish – cream body with a soft ridged texture and a hard shelled head. The larva usually burrows into the crown of the raphia palm, feeding on the young tissues, and sometimes destroys the growing point resulting in the death of the raphia palm tree (Opara *et al.*, 2012). In spite of their destructive attributes, the grubs of the African palm weevils are highly valued delicacies in western and Niger Delta regions of Nigeria, where they are either consumed raw or cooked (boiled and fried) (Opara *et al.*, 2012), while some are used for medicinal purposes (Onyeike *et al.*, 2005). Several nutrients such as protein, fatty acids, minerals (zinc and iron) and vitamins (thiamine and riboflavin) are known to be present in the palm grub (Chinweuba *et al.* 2011).

The aim and objective of this study was to ascertain the bacteriological quality and the antibiotic susceptibility of the bacterial flora associated with the processed *R. phoenicis* grubs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of roasted grubs

Freshly processed *R. phoenicis* were purchased from hawkers along Sapele road by Santana market, Benin City, Edo State and Amukpe-Sapele roundabout, Sapele, Delta State. Ten (10) roasted grubs were collected from the two locations in the month of February, 2015. The roasted grubs were placed in clean sterile polyethylene bags and wrapped in aluminum foil paper to prevent contamination and transported to the laboratory for appropriate microbial analysis.

Determination of the mean heterotrophic bacterial flora

The culturable heterotrophic bacterial count of the roasted grubs was determined using serial dilution and pour plate procedure as described by Roberts and Greenwood (2003). Unique bacterial isolates were characterized and identified by subjecting the cultures to a variety of relevant physiological and biochemical tests as described by Harley and Prescott (2002).

Evaluation of the antibiogram profiles of the bacterial isolates

The identified purified bacterial isolates were transferred to sterile peptone water under aseptic conditions and incubated for 10 h. The turbidities of the broth cultures were adjusted

to match an opacity standard; Barium sulphate and Tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid solution. The resulting broth culture had a microbial cell density of about 10^6 cfu. Muller Hinton agar plates were prepared and labeled appropriately. These plates were inoculated with the standardized microbial broth cultures by spread plate techniques (Harley and Prescott, 2002). The inoculated plates were left to dry for 30 mins. Commercially available antibiotic discs containing varying concentrations of several antibiotics; ceftazidime, ofloxacin, augmentin, cefloxime, cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin, nitrofurantoin, gentamicin and ciprofloxacin were placed at adequate distances on each of the seeded agar plates with the aid of sterile forceps. The plates were incubated at 35°C for 12h. The resultant visible zones of inhibition were measured. Distances lesser than 14 mm were regarded as resistant (R), while distances which ranged from 14 mm to 17 mm were indicated as intermediate (I). Zones of inhibition greater than 17 mm were recorded as susceptible (S) for the respective isolates (Harley and Prescott, 2002).

RESULTS

The mean heterotrophic bacterial bio-load associated with the processed *R. phoenicis* grubs is presented in Table 1. The mean bacterial counts recorded for grub samples collected within Benin City ranged from 1.1×10^3 cfu/g \pm 0.12 for S6 to 5.9×10^3 cfu/g \pm 3.20 for S2 (Table 1). The mean bacterial counts recorded for grub samples collected within Amukpe-Sapele ranged from 1.1×10^3 cfu/g \pm 3.10 for S20 to 3.0×10^3 cfu/g \pm 0.65 for S1 (Table 1). The total mean heterotrophic bacterial counts for all the respective sampled points in both Benin City and Amukpe-Sapele roundabout were 3.4×10^3 cfu/g \pm 1.71 and 2.0×10^3 cfu/g \pm 0.90 respectively (Table 1).

Seven bacterial isolates were associated with the sampled grubs collected from the sampling sites. The isolates included; *Staphylococcus* sp., *Micrococcus* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Enterococcus* sp., *Corynebacterium* sp., *Listeria* sp. and *Streptococcus* sp. (Table 2). *Bacillus* sp. and *Listeria* sp. were the most frequently isolated bacterial cultures from roasted grubs collected in Benin City while *Staphylococcus* sp. was the most dominant bacterial isolate present in majority of roasted grubs collected from Amukpe-Sapele road (Table 3). All the bacterial isolates from the grubs were resistant to ceftazidime and cefuroxime (Table 4).

There were marked differences between the antibiotic resistance patterns exhibited by the respective bacterial isolates identified from the sampling points; Benin City and Amukpe-Sapele (Table 4). *Corynebacterium* sp. isolated recovered from processed grubs collected within Benin City was sensitive to Nitrofurantoin and Ciprofloxacin while 50 % of the same isolate identified from grubs sampled from Amukpe-Sapele were resistant to same antibiotic (Table 4). A proportion of *Listeria* sp. (50 %) identified from roasted grubs sampled from Amukpe-Sapele were resistant to Gentamicin whilst all of the isolates (100%) present in grubs collected in Benin City were resistant towards the antibiotic (Table 4).

Table 1: Mean heterotrophic bacterial counts of the roasted grubs collected from Benin City and Amukpe-Sapele

Sampled sites within Benin City	Mean heterotrophic bacterial counts ($\times 10^3$ cfu/g \pm Std. deviation)	Sampled sites within Amukpe-Sapele roundabout	Mean heterotrophic bacterial counts ($\times 10^3$ cfu/g \pm Std. deviation)
S1	2.0 \pm 1.03	S11	3.0 \pm 0.65
S2	5.9 \pm 3.20	S12	3.1 \pm 3.54
S3	4.5 \pm 0.51	S13	1.2 \pm 5.70
S4	4.5 \pm 0.71	S14	1.2 \pm 2.40
S5	1.9 \pm 0.42	S15	1.2 \pm 1.70
S6	1.1 \pm 0.12	S16	1.9 \pm 2.82
S7	5.6 \pm 3.20	S17	1.3 \pm 1.40
S8	1.9 \pm 0.10	S18	2.8 \pm 1.41
S9	2.5 \pm 0.61	S19	2.9 \pm 0.61
S10	3.9 \pm 3.10	S20	1.1 \pm 3.10
Total Mean	3.4 \pm 1.71		2.0 \pm 0.90

Table 2: List of the tentatively characterized bacterial isolates

Benin City	Amukpe-Sapele
<i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.	<i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.
<i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.
<i>Enterococcus</i> sp.	<i>Listeria</i> sp.
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	<i>Streptococcus</i> sp.
<i>Listeria</i> sp.	

Table 3: Percentage frequency distribution of the bacterial isolates

Bacterial isolate	Benin City		Amukpe-Sapele	
	No of isolates	% occurrence	No isolates	% occurrence
<i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.	1	16.7	20	80
<i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	2	8.3	Nil	Nil
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	3	25	1	4
<i>Enterococcus</i> sp.	1	8.3	Nil	Nil
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	2	16.7	2	8
<i>Listeria</i> sp.	3	25	2	8
<i>Streptococcus</i> sp.	Nil	Nil	1	4
Total	12	100	25	100

Table 4: Antibiotic resistance patterns of the bacterial isolates

Location	No of isolate	% resistance							
		CN (10 µg)	CXM (5 µg)	OFL(5 µg)	AUG (30 µg)	NIT (30 µg)	CPR (5 µg)	CAZ (30 µg)	CRX (30 µg)
Benin City									
<i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.	1	1(0)	1(100)	1(0)	1(100)	1(0)	1(0)	1(100)	1(100)
<i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	2	2(0)	2(100)	2(0)	2(100)	2(0)	2(0)	2(100)	2(100)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	3	3(0)	3(100)	3(0)	3(100)	3(0)	3(0)	3(100)	3(100)
<i>Enterococcus</i> sp.	1	1(0)	1(100)	1(0)	1(100)	1(0)	1(0)	1(100)	1(100)
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	2	2(50)	2(100)	2(0)	2(100)	2(0)	2(0)	2(100)	2(100)
<i>Listeria</i> sp.	3	3(100)	3(0)	3(33.3)	3(66.6)	3(0)	3(100)	3(100)	3(100)
Amukpe-Sapele									
<i>Staphylococcus</i> sp.	20	20(100)	20(80)	20(0)	20(50)	20(65)	20(10)	20(100)	20(100)
<i>Micrococcus</i> sp.	Nil	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	3	3(66.5)	3(85)	3(0)	3(100)	3(0)	3(0)	3(100)	3(100)
<i>Enterococcus</i> sp.	Nil	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
<i>Corynebacterium</i> sp.	2	2 (50)	2(100)	2(0)	2 (100)	2(50)	2(50)	2(100)	2(100)

DISCUSSION

The microbiological qualities of vended food materials sold along the highways have always been called to question. Based on this premise, this investigation was carried out to ascertain the microbiological quality of grubs sold along one of the most important highways in the southern region of Nigeria. It is therefore not surprising that the roasted grubs collected from several vendors both within Benin City and Amukpe-Sapele roundabout were populated with a diverse group of culturable bacteria (Table 1 and 2). This trend could be attributable to the nutrient rich status of the processed mature grubs as the processed grubs are known to possess high moisture, protein and carbohydrate values (Elemo *et al.*, 2011; Opara *et al.*, 2012). Jay (1978) reported that the type and number of microorganisms present in a finished (prepared) food product is mainly impacted by the environment from where the food was originally obtained, the microbial quality of the food in its raw or unprocessed state and the prevailing sanitary conditions under which the food is handled and processed. Hartley, (1977) reported that microorganisms commonly associated with insect larvae differ and are related to the microorganisms associated with the palm and sap environments. The isolation of *Staphylococcus* sp. from the examined roasted grubs (Table 2 and 3) was in agreement with an earlier report by Opara *et al.* (2012) which identified the bacterial isolate from hawked roasted grub sampled from three selected zones of Amassoma rain forest in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Although there were variations in the antibiotic resistance patterns exhibited by the different strains of characterized roasted bug borne isolates, all the examined bacterial strains displayed multiple antibiotic resistance (Table 4). This worrisome trend is surprising given the fact that these grubs were harvested from the wild and the processing of these grubs i.e, subjecting the grubs to heat treatments would have negatively stressed the native bacterial populations present in the grubs. The expressed phenotypic multiple drug resistance exhibited by the grub borne isolates might be a reflection of the stress adaptation capabilities of these bacterial cultures. Capozzi *et al.* (2009) stated that stress conditions such as cold stress, heat stress, acid stress, freeze injury among others may trigger several mechanisms in bacterial cells which include; stress adaptation, cellular repair, application of response mechanisms and enhanced virulence.

The possible ingestion of roasted grubs populated with antimicrobial resistant and potentially pathogenic bacteria by unsuspecting consumers especially those with compromised immunity status is an immediate public health risk. There is an urgent need for relevant Governmental and non-Governmental agencies to educate and sensitize artisanal producers and hawkers of these grubs on cost effective ways to produce relatively sterile roasted grubs and observance of basic sanitary practices by the hawkers to prevent contamination of the grubs prior to sale to the consumer.

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